

Metamaterial-based vibration control for offshore wind turbines operating under multiple hazard excitation forces

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Abstract

Wind energy holds growing investment perspectives due to its renewable and sustainable energy production potential. The harvesting capability of wind turbines is directly related to their size. Therefore, those wind energy generators still encounter challenges related to excessive vibrations aggravated by environmental factors, compromising energy generation and resulting in fatigue damage and downtime. Various vibration control strategies have been explored to address these issues, with passive control emerging as a preferred choice due to its ease of manufacture, cost-effectiveness, and simple installation. Nevertheless, the limitations of these controls lie in their substantial size and weight associated with optimal installation positions for achieving a good performance. Recently, mechanical metamaterials have demonstrated tremendous advancements in efficiency regarding band isolation and vibration mitigation, coupled with enhanced manufacturing possibilities. Hence, this paper proposes a novel approach to control the vibration of wind turbines employing mechanical metamaterials in their design. A spectral approach is used to model the metamaterial turbine and its interaction with external excitations, such as wind, waves, and blade rotation. The numerical results show the efficiency of the metamaterial turbine by its tunable stopband features and vibration amplitude reduction under multiple hazard excitations, emphasising its superior suppressing vibrations compared to conventional tuned mass damper. Thus, the proposed wind turbine metastructures offer a compelling combination of effective vibration attenuation while reducing dynamic resonators' overall stiffness, mass, and size. The outcome advances wind turbine design and energy technology for reliable wind energy production.

Keywords: Passive control; Spectral method; Low-frequency vibration mitigation; Wind-Wave-Blade rotation force.

1. Introduction

The global renewable energy sector has experienced remarkable growth in response to energy crises and climate change concerns. Among the various renewable energy technologies, wind energy has emerged as a prominent sustainable and reliable alternative to conventional fossil fuel-based power generation. Notably, the wind industry, equipped with existing technology and significant unexploited potential, can reduce dependence on coal, oil, and gas, all while drawing substantial investments. Recent years have witnessed robust growth in the wind industry, with 2021 alone holding 93.6 GW of new installations, on top of 837 GW of the global wind power capacity. Projections indicate that the global wind turbine market could expand by US\$102.4 billion by 2030[1]. Ambitious plans are underway to

install new wind farms from 2022 to 2026, set to amplify production by over 116 GW [2], where anticipated growth lies primarily in offshore horizontal wind turbines in the deep sea.

Horizontal-axis wind turbines consist of a combination of assembled components, and the selection of materials and geometrical parameters has an impact on various factors such as the modal properties of the turbine, the dynamic and operational loads it can withstand, environmental considerations, and the installation site itself [3]. The intrinsic structural dynamic properties of wind turbines, featured by their high modal density, pose challenges for optimal design, especially in large turbines, where an in-depth understanding of their vibration characteristics is critical during the project phase associated with installation environmental conditions. Operating wind turbines at sea introduces many challenges, with excessive vibration warranting significant attention, which is aggravated by external loads, turbulence, shear, imbalances, waves, and more, compound the complex multi-directional and multi-coupling vibration phenomena [4, 5]. Hence, a recurring issue in wind turbines is excessive vibration resulting from operation or environmental conditions, precipitating malfunctions and potential damage to turbine components. Vibrations can trigger substantial deformations, affecting the nacelle, tower, blades, and drive-train and giving rise to operational noise and fatigue[6].

Effective strategies for controlling undesired vibration are crucial to ensure the long-term reliability of wind turbines. Hence, in recent years, substantial research has focused on integrating control devices to address challenges related to turbine vibration. Extensive research of structural control methods and recent advancements to mitigate vibration problems in wind turbines is presented in [7, 8]. The pros and cons of diverse vibration control methodologies have been discussed, along with their application and effectiveness in [9, 10]. Notably, the application of vibration control strategies varies across different wind turbine components, with research concentrating on towers [6], rotors [11], and blades [12, 13]. In recent years, significant interest has been in leveraging novel materials and designs to overcome vibration issues in wind turbine technology. Multiple research, including dampers, system controllers, and hybrid configurations, have been proposed to manage vibrations and increase turbine performance[7].

The tower and nacelle emerge as the most substantial wind turbine components, susceptible to wind, wave, and rotational blade forces. Researchers have formulated vibration control systems targeting multiple turbine elements simultaneously, with passive control strategies assuming prominence. For instance, large wind turbines have integrated optimal tuned mass dampers (TMDs) for vibration suppression[14, 15, 16]. Moreover, optimisation approaches employing TMDs and rotational inertial double-tuned mass dampers (RIDTMDs) have been harnessed, accounting for real wind distribution[17, 18]. Pendulum-tuned mass dampers (PTMDs) have emerged as a global vibration control solution for turbines[19, 20, 21, 22]. Jahangiri and Sun[23] innovatively integrated bidirectional PTMD vibration control with energy harvesting for offshore monopile wind turbines. Further the three-dimensional pendulum-tuned mass damper (3d-PTMD)[24, 25, 26], strategically addresses bidirectional vibration in monopile wind turbines. Additional innovation surfaces in double-response dampers, fusing tuned mass dampers with particle dampers to quell wind-induced vibrations in turbine towers[27]. TMDs have even been applied to mitigate wind-wave-earthquake excitations affecting the turbines in [28, 29, 30]. Researchers also explored multiple-tuned mass dampers (MTMDs) to manage multi-modal structural vibrations and combined loads[31, 7, 32, 33, 34]. The MTMD approach has been adopted for diverse wind turbine configurations, spanning bottom-fixed, monopile, and pentapod offshore structures, considering soil-structure interaction[35, 36]. MTMD strategies have also been employed for offshore wind turbine

vibration control under diverse hazards[37, 38]. In certain cases, MTMD systems simultaneously manage out-of-plane and in-plane vibrations [39, 40, 41, 42]. This diverse array of approaches exemplifies the ongoing attempt to effectively address vibration concerns in wind turbines, reinforcing their demand and performance.

Metamaterials, a class of functional materials, have quickly developed as a powerful and efficient mechanism for vibration control in engineering contexts. Recent progress in manufacturing technology has enabled the integration of metamaterials into engineering applications, providing customised design and optimisation possibilities for specific use cases. The past decade has seen rapid development in the use of metamaterials in engineering applications, with vibration control being one of the focal points aided by manufacturing innovations. Engineered metamaterials for vibration control commonly assume the form of periodic structures, incorporating resonators distributed throughout the structure. This arrangement grants superior vibration suppression within bandgap regions, outperforming the capabilities of traditional dynamic absorbers or tuned mass dampers[43]. A comprehensive overview of metamaterials and their applications in vibration control was presented in[44, 45, 46]. Local resonators, founded on the mechanical dynamic vibration absorber (DVA) concept, have attracted substantial attention for their efficacy within various structures. Investigative efforts published in [47, 48, 49, 50, 51] have explored bandgaps' behaviour and formation mechanisms in metamaterial beams designed with local resonant structures. This exploration has encompassed flexural vibration bandgaps, tunable flexural wave bandgaps, and extensive vibration attenuation made possible by incorporating multiple periodic arrays of local resonators into those structures. Metamaterial applied in slender and large structures have been proposed by Zhong et al.[52], where the authors investigated metamaterial I-Girder beams for vibration absorption in composite stayed bridges, and by Zhou et al.[51] that delved into tunable flexural wave bandgaps in prestressed elastic beams, exploiting periodic smart resonators. In cable and overhead transmission contexts, Machado et al. [53] employed the mechanical and graded metamaterial to effectively mitigate the vibration in single and multiple frequency ranges in broadband. In [54, 55], the authors incorporated multi-degree-of-freedom local resonators to mitigate and absorber impact forces, while [56, 57, 58] explored internal couplings between adjacent local resonators, inducing additional bandgaps in conventional acoustic and mechanical metamaterials.

Despite numerous applications and models dedicated to passive vibration control in wind turbines, there is a notable gap in the research literature concerning mechanical metamaterials' use to mitigate turbine vibration and achieve bandgap formation in low frequencies spanning single to multiple frequencies. This research direction remains unexplored within our knowledge, representing an open challenge that requires thorough investigation. Therefore, this paper proposes employing functional mechanical metamaterial to control the vibration of OWT. The main contribution of this research is the dynamic design of the metamaterial turbine (meta-turbine) and the use of the spectral method to model the metamaterial turbine. The turbine is tested under wind-wave-blade rotation loadings, simulating the operation environment of the OWT to address the efficiency of the proposed control. Then, vibration amplitude reduction of the metamaterial OWT under multiple hazard excitation achieves up to 30% associated with the small size resonators device compared to the conventional tuned damper mass (TMD) that reduces amplitude vibration by 7,8%. Therefore, the proposed metamaterial-based vibration control of a wind turbine offers a compelling combination of wide operational bandwidth and effective frequency attenuation while reducing the resonators' overall stiffness, mass, and size compared with conventional TMD. The overall structure of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents wind turbine metamaterial designed for vibration control modelled using the Spectral Element Method.

Section 3 introduces wind-wave loadings prescribed by IEC 61400-1 (IEC and IEC 61400-1, 2005), and their frequency characteristics and blade rotation simulation are covered. Section 4 showcases the numerical results, followed by the conclusion in Section 5. Analytical formulation to check the band gap formation is described in Appendix A, and the validation of the proposed meta-turbine within the finite element method is presented in Appendix B.

2. Wind turbine metamaterial designed for vibration control

The wind turbine modelled and selected to design the control based on the metamaterial is the NREL 5 MW offshore wind turbine (OWT) monopile three-bladed horizontal axis [59]. This turbine has properties well-defined in previous literature studies. The properties of the turbines are listed in Table 1. The tower height above the water level is 87.6 m, and the length of the hollow monopile foundation in the water (between the mean sea level (MSL) and the ground level) is 20 m. The monopile length buried in the soil is about 30 to 45 m [59]. Therefore, the present study considers the pile fully fixed at the ground level, not further complicating the metamaterial turbine design.

Wind turbine properties	Value	Wind turbine properties	Value
Max rater power	5MW	Rotor diameter	126 m
Tower heigth	87.6 m	Hub diameter	3 m
Rotor hub height	90 m	Tower top section diameter	3.87 m
Monopile height	20 m	Tower bottom diameter	6 m
Tower mass	347,460 Kg	Tower wall thickness	27-19 mm
Rotor mass (with hub)	110,000 Kg	Monopile wall thickness	27 mm
Nacelle mass	240,00 Kg	Nacelle inertia - Yaw axis	2,607,890 kg m ²
Rated speed (Cut-In)	6.9 - 12.1 rpm	Hub inertia - Low speed	115,926 kg m ²

Table 1: NREL 5 MW offshore wind turbine parameters[59].

Figure 1 (a) shows the 5 MW offshore wind turbine schematic representation, including the excitation forces (wind, blade rotation and wave). The dynamic modelling of the turbine considers the rotor-nacelle (RNA) assembly, which is modelled as a lumped mass placed at the tower top, as shown in Fig. 1 (b), and the spectral model representation is in Fig. 1 (c).

Figure 1: NREL 5 MW offshore wind turbine schematic representation(a). Simplification of the turbine for dynamic modelling purposes (b) and OWT spectral element model mesh (c).

2.1. OWT spectral element model

One of the benefits of using the spectral element method (SEM) is its ability to accurately represent a structure's dynamics with a small number of elements in the mesh, resulting in significant computational efficiency compared to the conventional Finite Element (FE) method. In this study, SEM is the base of our numerical model. The element shape functions are obtained from the exact solution of governing differential equations, and the dynamic system solutions were expressed in the frequency domain to improve solution accuracy. A two-dimensional spectral model of the NREL 5 MW turbine was implemented using Matlab, with the tower and monopile modelled by the beam element and the rotor-nacelle-blades as a lumped mass, Fig. 1 (c). The two-node spectral beam element's free-body diagram contains nodal displacements related to the transverse and slope displacements ($v(z, t)$, $\theta(z, t)$). The nodal forces shear and moments ($V(z, t)$, $M(z, t)$), respectively. The potential and kinetic energy applied to Hamilton's principle can be described as

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} [\delta(\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}) + \delta\mathcal{W}]dt = 0 \quad (1)$$

where the potential energy is

$$\mathcal{U} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L EI \frac{\partial^4 v(z, t)}{\partial z^4} dz \quad (2)$$

the kinetic energy considers the mass of the element tip. The nacelle on the tower's top is a lumped mass that acts as a filter, attenuating high-frequency terms while preventing low frequencies from passing through, thus obstructing the travel waves and serving as a boundary condition. The incident wave causes a reflected wave, and the two waves

superpose at the boundary to satisfy the boundary conditions, yielding

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \rho A \frac{\partial^2 v(z, t)}{\partial t^2} + m_n \delta(z - L) \frac{\partial^2 v(z, t)}{\partial t^2} dz \quad (3)$$

The virtual work due to the non-conservative forces is given by

$$\delta \mathcal{W} = \int_0^L q(z, t) \delta x(z, t) dz \quad (4)$$

where E , I , ρ , and A are Young's modulus, inertia moment, mass density per unit length, and cross-section area, respectively. The hysteretic damping is introduced into the beam formulation by adding the damping factor (η) into Young's modulus (E) so that $E = E(1 + i\eta)$, where $i = \sqrt{-1}$. The boundary conditions associated with the lumped mass [60] are expressed as

$$EI \frac{\partial^3 v(z = L, t)}{\partial z^3} = m_n \frac{\partial^2 v(z = L, t)}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

By applying the above Eqs. 3 and 5 into the Hamilton's principle, the equation of motion that represents the wind turbine is given as follows

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 v(z, t)}{\partial z^4} + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 v(z, t)}{\partial t^2} + m_n \delta(z - L) \frac{\partial^2 v(z, t)}{\partial t^2} = q(z, t) \quad (6)$$

where L is the OWT height, v and q are the transversal displacements and external load, respectively. Since SEM is formulated in the frequency domain, the Fourier transform is applied to convert the governing equations in the frequency domain. Hence, the displacement is expressed spectrally as

$$v(z, t) = \sum_n^N \hat{v}(z, \omega_n) e^{-i\omega_n t} \quad (7)$$

By replacing the spectral components of Eq. (7) into Eq.(6), the spectral representation of the OWT equation of motion in the frequency domain is obtained as

$$EI \frac{d^4 \hat{v}}{dz^4} + \omega^2 [\rho A + \tilde{m}_n \delta(z - L)] \hat{v} = \hat{q}$$

where $\tilde{m}_n = m_n/EI\beta^3$, $\delta(z - L)$ is Dirac's delta at $z = L$. The general solution of the spectral displacements follows the relationship

$$\hat{v}(z) = \sum_{i=1}^4 a_i e^{-ik_i z} = \mathbf{s}(z, \omega) \mathbf{a} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\mathbf{s}(z, \omega) = [e^{-ik_1 z}, e^{-ik_2 z}, e^{-ik_3 z}, e^{-ik_4 z}], \quad \mathbf{a} = [a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]^T$$

the homogeneous differential equation with constant properties along the beam length, which is written in the spectral form as

$$\frac{d^4 \hat{v}}{dz^4} - \beta^4 \hat{v} = 0, \quad \beta^2 = \omega \left(\frac{\rho A}{EI} \right)^{1/4} \quad (9)$$

and the solutions of the form $e^{-i\beta z}$, where the wavenumber β related to propagating and evanescent waves is $k_{1,3} = \pm\beta$ and $k_{2,4} = \pm i\beta$, respectively. By considering a finite element with length l_e , the spectral nodal displacements in terms of a_j , which satisfy the boundary conditions of the system, where the spectral nodal displacements (\hat{v}) and slopes ($\hat{\phi}$)

are obtained at the nodes so that at node 1 (left end, $z = 0$) and node 2 (right end, $z = l_e$). Applying the boundary conditions, the displacement in a matrix form is written as

$$\mathbf{d} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_1 \\ \hat{\phi}_1 \\ \hat{v}_2 \\ \hat{\phi}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}(0) \\ \hat{v}'(0) \\ \hat{v}(l_e) \\ \hat{v}'(l_e) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} s(0, \omega) \\ s'(0, \omega) \\ s(l_e, \omega) \\ s'(l_e, \omega) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{G}(\omega) \mathbf{a} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\mathbf{G}(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & e^{-ikl_e} & e^{-kl_e} \\ -ik & -k & ie^{-ikl_e}k & e^{-kl_e}k \\ e^{-ikl_e} & e^{-kl_e} & 1 & 1 \\ -ie^{-ikl_e}k & -e^{-kl_e}k & ik & k \end{bmatrix}$$

The frequency-dependent displacement within an element is interpolated from the nodal displacement vector \mathbf{d} by eliminating the constant vector \mathbf{a} from equation (10) express the solution of the form $v(z, \omega) = \mathbf{g}(z, \omega) \mathbf{d}$, where $\mathbf{g}(z, \omega)$ is shape function described by

$$\mathbf{g}(z, \omega) = \mathbf{s}(z, \omega) \mathbf{G}^{-1}(\omega) = \mathbf{s}(z, \omega) \mathbf{\Gamma}(\omega) \quad (11)$$

By considering $\rho A \omega^2 = EI k^4$ and substituting in Eq. 3, the weak form can be derived from weight-integral to obtain the dynamic stiffness matrix for the two-nodes beam element with an added mass on the tip as

$$\mathbf{S}(\omega) = EI \left[\int_0^L \mathbf{g}''(z)^T \mathbf{g}''(z) dx + k^4 \int_0^L \mathbf{g}(z)^T \mathbf{g}(z) dz + \omega^2 k^3 m_n \right] \quad (12)$$

where $'$ expresses the spatial partial derivative. The monopile can be modelled with the tower's continuous geometry, therefore, the one element formulated in Eq. (13) fully describes the turbine. The OWT NREL 5MW monopile [59] has a tower assumed with a tapered geometry considering a bottom diameter of 6 m and top diameter of 3.87 m. We modelled the monopile tower's tapered geometry in this case by reducing each beam element's cross-sectional area from element one (bottom) to the top. The base elements (three in total) are similar in cross-section, with a diameter of 6 m, and their proportional diameter and thickness decrease as the cross-section decreases up to the top, whereas the last element (number 13) has the top diameter. The spectral mesh consists of 13 spectral elements, where the beam element is modelled as [61]

$$\mathbf{S}_b(\omega) = EI \left[\int_0^L \mathbf{g}''(z)^T \mathbf{g}''(z) dx + k^4 \int_0^L \mathbf{g}(z)^T \mathbf{g}(z) dz \right] \quad (13)$$

and the beam with a lumped mass by Eq. (13). The spectral OWT draft model is shown in Figure 1, including the external forces of wind, rotation of the blades (1P), and wave action.

2.2. Metastructure control modelling

Due to its simplicity and effectiveness, a tuned mass damper (TMD) or dynamic vibration absorber is widely used as a passive control mechanism for mitigating vibrations in wind turbines. Generally, this control system operates at up to two resonant frequencies simultaneously, and its effectiveness depends on the optimal installation position within the structure and its overall characteristics. Various structures have applied metamaterials to enhance their properties

and structural functions. This study aims to investigate the application of metamaterials for mitigating wind turbine vibrations, as illustrated in Figure 3. Two designed resonators are employed in the control system, operating at the wind turbine's first and second resonant frequencies, namely 0.27 Hz and 2.39 Hz, respectively. These resonators are affixed inside the turbine's tower in three configurations, addressing single-frequency fore-aft vibrations (Figure 2a LHS) or either fore-aft or side-to-side vibrations (Figure 2a RHS), and multiple-frequency control of fore-aft vibrations (Figure 2b).

Figure 2: Schematic top view section drawing of the wind turbine metastructure tower with the resonator installed: a) side-to-side (RHS) or side-side and fore-aft (LHS), b) multi-frequency control.

The resonant frequencies of the OWT are well-defined and exhibit distinct intervals from one another. The design of the control mechanisms and their specific properties are delineated separately, with the configurations of the resonators shown in Fig. 2. Within the OWT metastructure, a total of N -resonators are placed within a designated subdomain, where $\Delta L_j = \int_{L_j} dL$ represents the length of subdomain L_j . The spring coefficient of each resonator in the metastructure design is assumed to be uniform. In contrast, the mass of each resonator is determined by $m_r = \epsilon m \Delta L$ [48], with the mass ratio denoted as $\epsilon = \sum_{p=1}^N m_r / \int_L m(x) dL$, for $m(x)$ being the mass density at a point in the domain. The equation of motion governing the resonators is as follows

$$m_r \ddot{u}_r(t) + k_r u_r(t) + m_r \ddot{w}(x, p, t) = 0 \quad r = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (14)$$

where $w(x, p, t)$ is the displacement of a point with position vector r related to the turbine tower (primary system), k_r , m_r , and $u_r(t)$ are, respectively, the stiffness, mass, and displacement of the p^{th} resonator relative to the principal structure. The relative displacement expressed by $u_r = (\mathbf{u}_r - w_{x_p})$, represents the displacement of each resonator r^{th} concerning the relative displacement of the principal structure (w_{x_p}). The tuned frequency of the resonator can be expressed as

$$\omega_r = \sqrt{\frac{k_r}{m_r}} \quad r = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (15)$$

By neglecting the displacement of a point on the primary system (turbine), the governing equation for the absorber can then be written as $(\mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}$. The variables \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{M} are the stiffness and mass matrices, \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector, and \mathbf{f} is the forcing vector, which are written as

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} k_r & -k_r \\ -k_r & k_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{u} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ u_1 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f} = \begin{Bmatrix} f_0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where u_0 and u_1 are, respectively, the displacements of the attachment point on the turbine tower and the absorber mass, and f_0 is the reaction force from the tower. The condensed form of the equation of motion is defined as

$f_0 = D_0 u_0$. The D_0 may be rewritten differently depending on the purposes of derivation [49]. For the turbine case, we assumed as

$$D_0 = \frac{k_r - k_r^2}{(k_r - \omega^2 m_r)} \quad (17)$$

The resonator is attached at the left end of the spectral element ($z = l_e$), and the D_0 sum in the degree of freedom related to the position attached to the resonators. The mass and damping ratios of the resonators are the key parameters that can significantly influence the effectiveness of control systems. The control in multiple resonate frequencies can be considered by attaching local resonators with multiple degrees of freedom (\bar{n} -DOF) to the principal structure [62, 53, 63]. Hence, for multiple frequencies control the equations of motion for the \bar{n} -resonators are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} m_r^{(1)} \ddot{u}_r^{(1)}(t) + k_r^{(1)} u_r^{(1)}(t) + m_r \ddot{w}(x, p, t) &= 0 \\ m_r^{(2)} \ddot{u}_r^{(2)}(t) + k_r^{(2)} [u_r^{(2)}(t) - u_r^{(1)}(t)] + k_r^{(3)} [u_r^{(3)}(t) - u_r^{(2)}(t)] &= 0 \\ &\vdots \\ m_r^{(\bar{n})} \ddot{u}_r^{(\bar{n})}(t) + k_r^{(\bar{n})} [u_r^{(\bar{n})}(t) - u_r^{(\bar{n}-1)}(t)] &= 0 \quad r = 1, 2, \dots, S, \quad \bar{n} = 1, 2, \dots, \bar{N} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $k_r^{\bar{n}}$, $m_r^{\bar{n}}$, and $u_r^{\bar{n}}(t)$ are, respectively, the stiffness, mass, and displacement of the r^{th} resonator at \bar{n} -DOF, \bar{N} is the total number of degree of freedom of each multi-resonator, $u_r^{(1)} = (\mathbf{u}_r^{(1)} - w_{x_p})$ and the tuned frequency of each resonator is calculated by

$$\omega_r^{\bar{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{k_r^{\bar{n}}}{m_r^{\bar{n}}}} \quad (19)$$

and the condensed form of the equation of motion for multiple-DOFs yields

$$D_0 = \sum_{p=1}^{\bar{N}} \frac{k_r^{\bar{n}} - (k_r^{\bar{n}})^2}{(k_r^{\bar{n}} - \omega^2 m_r^{\bar{n}})} \quad \bar{N} = 1, 2, \dots, \bar{n} \quad (20)$$

The hysteretic damping was assumed on the resonator's springs because this damping model is usually associated with dry friction appearing inside the material. In this case, the hysteretic damping model of the resonators assumes complex stiffness of the form $k_r = \bar{k}_r(1 + i\zeta)$. The flexural vibration of a finite beam with a length of l_e is simulated employing the SEM, discussed in section 2.1. The unit cell of the periodic system for dynamic modelling is assumed; therefore, there are diverse options for the structure of this unit cell [49], in this context, we opt for a configuration that consists of a unit-cell beam element attached to the resonator to the right end of the beam. This choice establishes the stiffness dynamic matrix for the unit cell as follows

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}_{ll} & \mathbf{D}_{lr} \\ \mathbf{D}_{rl} & \mathbf{D}_{rr} + \mathbf{D}_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & D_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

the subscripts l and r denote the left and right sides of the unit cell, the dynamic description condensed, yielding $\mathbf{D}(\omega)\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{F}$, and the sub-matrices of matrix \mathbf{D} are

$$\mathbf{D}_{ll} = \begin{bmatrix} S_b^{11} & S_b^{12} \\ S_b^{21} & S_b^{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D}_{lr} = \mathbf{D}_{rl}^T = \begin{bmatrix} S_b^{13} & S_b^{14} \\ S_b^{23} & S_b^{24} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D}_{rr} = \begin{bmatrix} S_b^{33} & S_b^{34} \\ S_b^{43} & S_b^{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

where S_b defines the spectral element matrix component.

3. Excitation forces

The stochastic component's power spectrum density (PSD) arising from turbulent wind and waves during operational conditions replicates the 5-MW OWT environment [59]. This analysis omits soil effects and considers the heights of individual nodes, as illustrated in Fig. 1(c). Meanwhile, the PSD of rotational conditions is assessed at the bending moment of the blade root, utilising the theoretical framework outlined by Burton[64]. This framework encompasses considerations such as rotor chord, airfoil shape, rotor twist, and blade count. The wind and wave-induced environmental action PSD is evaluated based on Kaimal and JONSWAP spectra. This section reports the rotationally sampled spectrum on blades and offers an analytical overview of wind and wave spectra.

3.1. Wind load

The wind forces encountered along the tower's vertical extent showcase fluctuations, and these forces can be deconstructed into a consistent average wind force and a varying component. To capture the attributes of this fluctuating wind velocity, the EIC Kaimal turbulence spectrum is utilised to construct the power spectral density function. This spectrum serves as a representation for the time-evolving inflow patterns, as stipulated by both the International Electrotechnical Commission's specifications[65] and DNV-OS-J101[66]. The spectrum's definition is as follows

$$S_{u_i u_i}(f) = \frac{4L_\kappa \sigma_\kappa^2 / \bar{U}}{(1 + 6fL_\kappa / \bar{U})^{5/3}} \quad (22)$$

where f is the circular frequency, standard deviation σ_κ and integral scale parameter L_κ are given in Table 2, the turbulence intensity's reference value $\sigma_1 = I_{ref}(0.75U_{hub} + 5.6)$, and the longitudinal turbulence scale parameter $\Lambda_1 = 0.8\sigma_1$ [65], where I_{ref} is the reference value of turbulence intensity. The wind velocity is obtained by the wind logarithm profile

$$\bar{U}(z) = \bar{U}_{ref} \left(\frac{z}{z_{ref}} \right)^\beta \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{U}_{ref} = 12\text{m/s}$ is the average velocity at reference height $z_{ref} = 87.6\text{ m}$, z is the vertical coordinate, and $\beta = 0.2$ is the wind shear (or power law) exponent.

Velocity component, κ	fore-aft	side-to-side	up-down
Standard deviation, σ_κ	σ_1	$0.8\sigma_1$	$0.5\sigma_1$
Integral scale, L_κ	$8.1\Lambda_1$	$2.7\Lambda_1$	$0.66\Lambda_1$

Table 2: Kaimal turbulence spectral parameters for velocity directions, for $\kappa = 1$.

In the case of a continuous linear structure such as the tower, the wind loads experienced at distinct positions along the tower manifest variations, yet certain resemblances are present. This phenomenon is recognised as the spatial correlation effect. Typically, a spatial coherency loss function is employed to characterise this phenomenon. The power spectrum of modal fluctuating drag forces, which encompasses the impact of the spatial correlation effect, is formulated as follows [41]

$$S_{f_i f_j}(f) = (C_d \rho_a A \bar{U})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N S_{u_i u_j}(f) v_i v_j \phi^2 \quad (24)$$

where $C_d = 1.2$ is the drag coefficient, $\rho_a = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is the air density, A is the total area of the tower exposed to the wind, i and j are the different positions along the tower, v is the mean wind velocities at specified locations, and ϕ is the aerodynamic admittance considered a unity. The cross PSD function ($S_{u_i u_j}$) of wind velocity between the specified locations is expressed as

$$S_{u_i u_j}(f) = \sqrt{S_{u_i u_i} S_{u_j u_j} \text{coh}(i, j, f)} \quad (25)$$

in which $S_{u_i u_i}$ and $S_{u_j u_j}$ are the wind velocity auto PSDs, and $\text{coh}(i, j, f)$ is the spatial coherency loss function between locations given by

$$\text{coh}(i, j, f) = \exp\{-12\Delta_z[(f/\bar{U})^2 + (0.12/L_c)^2]\} \quad (26)$$

where $L_c = 8.1\Lambda_1$ is the coherence scale parameter, and Δ_z is the vertical distance between i and j positions.

3.2. Aerodynamic loads of blades during operation

The random loads acting on the blade due to short-term wind fluctuations, which occur in the frequency domain, are determined through a combination of a probability distribution and the energy distribution within a power spectrum. The procedure for calculating the rotational spectrum, as expounded by Burton et al.[64], relies on the standard deviation of the blade root bending moment, defined as

$$S_{BM}(f) = \left(\frac{1}{2}\rho_a\Omega\frac{dC_l}{d\alpha}\right)^2 \sum_i \sum_j S_u^o(r_i, r_j, f) c(r_i) c(r_j) r_i^2 r_j^2 (\Delta_r o)^2 \quad (27)$$

where C_l is the lift aerodynamic coefficient of the blade, α is the wind to blade angle of attack, Ω is the rotor rotation frequency (assumed 12.1 rpm), $c(r_i)$ and $c(r_j)$ is the chord length at radii r_i and r_j with $\Delta_r o$ is the distance between the radii. The rotational sampled cross-spectrum in the selected points of the rotating blade is

$$S_u^o(r_i, r_j, f) = 2 \int_0^T \kappa_u^o(r_i, r_j, \tau) \cos(2\pi f\tau) d\tau \quad (28)$$

and the cross-correlation function κ_u^o as

$$\kappa_u^o(r_i, r_j, \tau) = \frac{2\sigma_u^2}{\Gamma(1/3)} \left(\frac{s}{2.68L_\kappa}\right)^{1/3} \left[K_{1/3} \left(\frac{s}{1.34L_\kappa}\right) - 0.5K_{2/3} \left(\frac{s}{1.34L_\kappa}\right)^2 \left(\frac{r_i^2 + r_j^2 - 2r_i r_j \cos(\Omega\tau/2)}{s^2}\right)^2 \right] \quad (29)$$

where $s = (\bar{U}^2\tau^2 + r_i^2 + r_j^2 - 2r_i r_j \cos(\Omega\tau))^{1/2}$, $L_\kappa = 3.5\Lambda_1$ for the isotropic model turbulence. By assuming $r_i = r_j$, and applying the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) to find the integral of the Fourier transform pair of a rotating blade under the limits of integration are altered to 0, T with $\kappa_u(r, t)$ set equal to $\kappa_u^o(r, T - \tau)$ for $\tau > T/2$, the rotationally sampled spectrum DFT is expressed by

$$S_u^o(r_i, r_j, f_p) = 2T \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{p=0}^{N-1} \kappa_u^{*o}(r_i, r_j, pT/N) \cos(2\pi f_p/N) \right] \quad (30)$$

where N is the number of points in the time series of $\kappa_u^{*o}(r, pT/N)$ (the asterisk denotes that $\kappa_u^o(r, \tau)$ is ‘reflected’ for $\tau > T/2$), and the PSD is calculated at the frequencies $f_p = p/T$ for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$.

3.3. Wave dynamics

For wave dynamics, JONSWAP (Joint North Sea Wave Project - S_{JS}) PSD is described as [65]

$$S_{JS}(n) = C(\gamma) \cdot S_{PM}(n) \cdot \gamma^\alpha \quad (31)$$

where $\alpha = \exp[-((f - f_p)^2)/(2\sigma^2 f_p^2)]$, being $\sigma = 0.07$ for $f \leq f_p$ or $\sigma = 0.09$ for $f > f_p$, for f_p representing the wave peak frequency ($f_p = 0.1\text{Hz}$), f the frequency, and S_{PM} is the Pierson Moskowitz PSD expressed by

$$S_{PM}(f) = 0.3125 H_s^2 f_p^4 f^{-5} \exp\left[-1.25 \left(\frac{f_p}{f}\right)^4\right], \quad (32)$$

where, the significant wave height is done by H_s and the peak frequency $f_p = 1/T_p$, with the peak period T_p . Expressing T_p and H_s as a function of meter and second, respectively, the normalising factor $C(\gamma) = 1 - 0.287 \ln(\gamma)$ is a function of peak-shape parameter γ , defined as,

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} 5 & , \text{ for } T_p/\sqrt{H_s} \leq 3.6, \\ \exp(5.75 - 1.15T_p/\sqrt{H_s}) & , \text{ for } 3.6 \leq T_p/\sqrt{H_s} \leq 5, \\ 1 & , \text{ for } T_p/\sqrt{H_s} > 5, \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

An important relation used in the analysis of the dynamic response of any system to random or spectral excitation is that the auto-spectral density (PSD) of the response of a system, ${}^{PSD}\mathbf{S}(\omega)$, to an excitation input ${}^{PSD}\mathbf{S}_{fo}(\omega)$ is given by

$${}^{PSD}\mathbf{S}(\omega) = |\mathbf{H}(\omega)|^2 {}^{PSD}\mathbf{S}_{fo}(\omega) \quad (34)$$

where the function $\mathbf{H}(\omega) = \mathbf{S}^{-1}(\omega)$ is the transfer function of the dynamic response.

4. Numerical results

The metastructures designed to mitigate the first and second vibration modes of the NREL 5 MW offshore wind turbine (OWT) are discussed in this section. We explore three different metastructure configurations: one places the metamaterial on top, covering a quarter of the tower's length (referred to as the 'top' configuration, shown in fig.3d); another arrangement installs the resonator from the top to the middle of the tower (referred to as the 'mid' configuration, shown in fig.3e); the last configuration involves placing the resonators periodically along the wind turbine's tower (referred to as the 'along' configuration, shown in fig. 3f). The turbine metastructure is then compared with the classical TMD control configurations installed on top and in the middle of the tower to mitigate the turbine's first and second resonant frequencies, respectively. A hysteric damping factor of $\zeta = 0.03$ is applied to the resonator's spring. The designed controls operate at the tuned resonant frequencies of 0.27 Hz and 2.39 Hz. The total mass ratio varies from 1% to 50%, covering a range of mass ratios, resonator positions and quantities. An excitation force with a unitary magnitude is applied at the free end (interface point-10, see fig. 3b). The receptance responses are estimated along the interface of the turbine's tower, guided by points 0 to 10 in Fig. 3a.

Figure 3: Physical and schematic drawing wind turbine metastructure. a) Simplified wind turbine metastructure, b) TMD control installed at the top of the WT, c) TMD control installed on the middle of the WT, d) Along-metastructure WT, e) Mid-metastructure WT, and f) Top-metastructure WT.

To date, the control strategies examined in the literature have positioned the TMD at the top of the wind turbine, as shown in fig. 3b, for a logical reason, referent to the substantial displacement of the tower's point in the first frequency mode shape. In the case of the second mode, the larger amplitude is situated in the middle of the tower, as shown in fig.3c. The TMD control approach effectively targets the desired frequency and bandwidth control. However, placing these individual TMDs at these specific points necessitates a trade-off, implying a considerably larger geometry involving the addition of a significant mass and stiffness associated with the TMD, typically ranging from 5% to 28% of the turbine's total mass. The construction, installation, and maintenance of these TMDs remain challenging due to the added mass and space constraints within the nacelle or inside the turbines. Therefore, utilising metamaterials for mitigating WT vibrations introduces an innovative design approach. This method reduces the complexity of the control process and devices by substantially reducing the resonators' mass, all while upholding control efficiency.

Table 3 presents the resonator control mass corresponding to the mass ratio (ϵ). In the classical TMD control approach, the resonator mass varies from 6.975 to 348.730 Kg, covering mass ratios from 1% to 50%. With the metamaterial solution, assuming 7 resonators, the mass of each reduces from 996 to 49.819 Kg depending on the control mass ratio (ϵ). With 13 resonators, each resonator's mass ranges from 537 to 26.826 Kg, and for 26 resonators, it further reduces to 258 to 13.413 Kg. From the perspective of mass ratios using the TMD, our metamaterial solution maintains the same added mass. From the perspective of each control device mass, the resonators can be kept small in the metamaterial application, facilitating ease of manufacturing, installation, and better integration within the turbine.

In conventional practice, dynamic TMDs and resonators are designed to operate at specific frequencies. The dynamic interaction between resonators and the primary structure leads to a bifurcation in the controlled resonance mode, introducing additional degrees of freedom around the targeted mode shape. Consequently, secondary resonance frequencies emerge to the left and right of the operational frequency of the primary system being controlled by these resonators. While this passive vibration control method demonstrates a well-defined operating range, straying beyond this range can lead to undesirable consequences, notably amplifying neighbouring mode amplitudes.

Number of resonator	Mass ratio[ϵ in %] - Mass of each resonator [Kg]								
	$\epsilon =1$	$\epsilon =5$	$\epsilon =10$	$\epsilon =15$	$\epsilon =20$	$\epsilon =25$	$\epsilon =30$	$\epsilon =40$	$\epsilon =50$
1	6.975	34.873	69.746	10.4619	13.9492	17.4365	209.238	278.984	348.730
7	996	4.982	9.964	14.946	19.928	24.909	29.892	39.855	49.819
13	537	2.683	5.365	8.048	10.730	13.413	16.095	21.461	26.826
26	258	1.341	2.683	4.024	5.365	6.707	8.048	10.731	13.413

Table 3: Mass of each resonator(mass ratio) associated with the number of resonators considered for each configuration used to control the first, second, and first-second resonant frequencies.

Figure 4 compares the OTW's receptance response calculated on the top for various control strategies, TMD, top-, mid-, and along-metastructure, in managing the first resonant frequency control. The TMD and top metastructure, illustrated in Figs.4a and 4b, effectively govern the first frequency without influencing other mode shapes. Figures 4c and 4d show the mid and along metastructures, which exhibit minor interaction with the second mode. Fig.4f presents a zoomed view of the first frequency domain, comparing the uncontrolled turbine, TMD control, and metastructures with mass ratios of 1%, 15%, and 30%, respectively. Similarly, Fig.4f offers a detailed perspective, comparing the uncontrolled turbine, TMD control, and metastructures with mass ratios of 5%, 20%, and 40%. Fig. 4g further delves into this frequency range and compares the uncontrolled turbine, TMD control, and metastructures with mass ratios of 10%, 25%, and 50%. In these figures, the TMD control is represented by a solid-dotted line, the top metastructure by a solid line, the mid metastructure by a dashed line, and the along metastructure by a dotted line. The TMD demonstrates the broadest frequency bandwidth split, followed by the top, mid, and along meta-turbine configurations. The top meta-turbine maintains alignment with the TMD's control bandwidth up to a mass ratio of 15%. The TMD's optimal performance is directly related to installation position and mass ratio, which, in this analysis, is positioned on top of the tower for first-mode control and in the middle for second-mode control.

Figure 4: OWT's receptance response with control targeting at first resonant frequency and mass ratio varying between $\epsilon = 1$ to 50% for a) TMD control installed on the top of WT, b) top-metastructure, c) mid-metastructure, and d) along-metastructure. Zoomed view of the first frequency range comparing the uncontrolled turbine against: e) TMD and metastructures with $\epsilon = 1\%$, 15%, and 30%; f) TMD and metastructures with $\epsilon = 5\%$, 20%, and 40%; and g) TMD and metastructures $\epsilon = 10\%$, 25%, and 50%. In managing the first resonant frequency control. The solid-dotted line represents the TMD control, the solid line the top-metastructure, the dashed line the mid-metastructure, and the dotted line the along-metastructure.

Figure 5 compares the TMD and turbine metastructure configurations to control the second resonant frequency, where Figs.5a and 5b illustrate the TMD and top metastructure controls, respectively, while Fig.5c demonstrates control through the mid metastructure, and Fig.5d shows the along configuration. It is important to note that the top and mid metastructure turbine induce some shifts in the first mode, which require consideration in scenarios involving external loads that often operate within lower frequency ranges. Figures 5e,5f, and 5g present detailed comparisons at the second resonant frequency, showcasing the responses of the uncontrolled turbine, TMD-controlled,

and metastructure-controlled turbines at different mass ratios (1, 15, 30%; 5, 20, 40%; 10, 25, 50%, respectively). TMD demonstrates these figures' broadest frequency bandwidth split when optimally placed, followed by the top, mid, and along metastructure configurations. Notably, the middle meta-turbine aligns with the TMD's control bandwidth up to a mass ratio of 15%.

Figure 5: OWT's receptance response with control targeting the second resonant frequency and mass ratio varying between $\epsilon = 1$ to 50% for a) TMD control installed on the top of WT, b) top-metastructure, c) mid-metastructure, and d) along-metastructure. View of both frequency ranges comparing the uncontrolled turbine against: e) TMD and metastructures with $\epsilon = 1\%$, 15% , and 30% ; f) TMD and metastructures with $\epsilon = 5\%$, 20% , and 40% ; and g) TMD and metastructures with $\epsilon = 10\%$, 25% , and 50% in managing the first resonant frequency control. The solid-dotted line represents the TMD control, the solid line the top-metastructure, the dashed line the mid-metastructure, and the dotted line the along-metastructure.

Figure 6a presents a receptance response heatmap correlating with the mass ratio of the uncontrolled turbine. Further insights are provided through Figures 6b,6c, and6d, which present receptance response heatmaps for the first

mode shape across the top, mid, and along metastructure turbine configurations, respectively. Similarly, Figures 6e,6f, and6g illustrate the heatmaps for both modes within the top-, mid-, and along-configurations. These maps effectively demonstrate the finite structure’s local bandgap formation, with the dark blue areas representing the indicative bandgap regions. The metastructure of the turbine showcases bandgap formation with the designed LR (local resonance) bandgap frequencies at 0.27 Hz and 2.39 Hz. This bandgap initiation commences from a mass ratio of 5% and gradually expands its bandwidth to encompass the entire 50% ratio range assumed in this analysis. The broadband size remains consistently large, irrespective of mass ratio variations. Corresponding with the outcomes presented in Figures 4 and 5, it is evident that the top metastructure configuration delivers a broader bandwidth for first mode control, while the mid metastructure configuration outperforms the second mode. A distinct shifting resonance frequency effect is also observable as a horizontal yellow line traversing the heatmap. This line indicates the resonant frequency split variation in mode shape position as the mass ratio increases.

Figure 6: Heatmap of the receptance response (tip displacement) versus mass ratio for a) Uncontrolled turbine, controlling the first resonant frequency with b) top-metastructure, c) mid-metastructure, and d) along-metastructure; and controlling the second resonant frequency with e) top-metastructure, f) mid-metastructure, and g) along-metastructure.

For multiple modes mitigation, specific stiffness values were established for each mode while maintaining a consistent mass, similar to the approach used in single-mode control. Receptance response and heatmap analyses of the top metamaterial turbine are presented in Figures 7a and 7d. Similarly, Figures 7b and 7e concern to the mid metastructure configuration, while Fig.7c and 7f correspond to the along metastructure arrangement. The local bandgap formation of the multi-frequency metamaterial turbine shown on the heatmap demonstrated the multiple-mode control operating at tuned frequencies 0.27 and 2.39 Hz. For the multiple-control design, the mid-metastructure configuration emerges as the most optimal solution, considering factors such as bandwidth and the implications of mass distribution in the case of the along meta turbine.

Figure 7: OWT's receptance response with control targeting the first and second resonant frequencies and mass ratios varying between 1 to 50% for a) top-metastucture, b) mid-metastucture, and c) along-metastucture. Heatmap of the receptance response (tip displacement) versus mass ratio for a) top-metastucture, b) mid-metastucture, and c) along-metastucture.

Figure 8: Stiffness values of each resonator in the function of the mass ratio and resonator numbers to control: a) single and b) multiple target frequencies.

The design of the resonator's dynamic properties is linked to the mass ratio and the desired target frequencies for control. The mass ratio varies from 5 to 50% of the turbine mass, encompassing both first- and second-mode shapes needing control. In Figure 8a, the stiffness values of each resonator are described against the mass ratio for the case of first mode control. Among these, the TMD control requires the highest stiffness, followed by the metaturbines with 3, 7, 13, and 26 resonators. The result of the metastructure design reflects a decrease in stiffness values as the number of resonators increases, consequently reducing the control device size and weight. A similar consideration applies to the multiple control scenario, as illustrated in Fig. 8b. Apart from bandwidth control, the design of resonators plays

a crucial role in the overall control strategy from the manufacture and installation point of view. In contrast to the conventional TMD control, the wind turbine metastructure offers the combination of a wide operational bandwidth and frequency attenuation, achieved with reduced stiffness and size of the resonators.

4.1. Bandgap formation

The mechanical and acoustic metamaterial concept relies on the theoretical base of infinite resonators, where a bandgap is achieved as n (number of resonators) approaches infinity. In practical implementations, n assumes finite values, as discussed in [48]. The mass ratio significantly influences the bandwidth of attenuation, which becomes saturated and cannot be expanded by increasing the mass. Consequently, all control strategies induce a bifurcation in the target mode shape, creating a localised bandgap. This local bandgap region represents a frequency band where elastic waves cannot propagate, offering effective vibration isolation.

The formation of the bandgap through the analysis of general linear attachments using the modal parameters of the plain (primary) structure can be assessed using the root locus technique, as proposed in [48]. The verification of local bandgap occurrence is achieved by strategically positioning the poles and zeros in the feedforward transfer function and extracting the relationship between the response and force of the resonators. When an infinite number of resonators are distributed across the structure, each mode shape of the basic structure is associated with two resonant frequencies, one falling below the bandgap frequency range and the other above the target frequency. These resonant frequencies correspond to the two branches of the root locus with $Im(H) > 0$ and represent distinct mode shapes of the structure with resonators. One mode aligns the primary structure in phase with the resonators, while the other places the primary structure out of phase with the resonators. The roots of the new resonant frequencies associated with each mode are briefly described in Appendix A.

Figure 9: Resonant frequencies of the turbine metastructure as a function of resonant frequencies of the primary turbine for a) single control with $\epsilon = 1$ and b) multiple control with $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 0.5$. The grey regions indicate the formation of an LR bandgap.

Figure 9 illustrates the open bandgap, highlighted by the grey area and bounded by resonant frequencies. This characterisation is based on the target resonant frequency, considering a mass ratio of $\epsilon = 1$ for the single-DOF resonator and $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 0.5$ for the multiple-DOF resonators. The boundary values of these frequencies offer valuable insights into the formation of the local bandgap. The higher resonance, denoted as ω^+ , reaches its minimum value at $\sqrt{1 + \epsilon} \rightarrow \Omega_n = 0$ and subsequently increases unboundedly with Ω_n , converging to $\omega^+ = \Omega_n$ as $\Omega_n \rightarrow \infty$. On the other hand, the lower resonance, labelled as ω^- , starts at a minimum of 0 as $\Omega_n \rightarrow 0$ and gradually approaches $\omega/\omega_r = 1$ as $\Omega_n \rightarrow \infty$. This frequency range effectively delineates the bounds of the local bandgap, offering a straightforward means

of identifying the bandgap within a desired frequency range. The root polynomial returns two roots or frequencies for single-DOF resonators, while the multiple-DOF resonators have three roots. The figure demonstrates that the limiting value of these frequencies estimates the one and two locally resonant bandgaps represented by the shaded in grey.

4.2. Vibration control under multiple hazards excitation forces

The responses of the wind turbine to multiple hazardous forces, taking into account the PSD of the rotating blades, waves, and along-wind forces applied to the OWT, are shown in Fig.1(c). The wind velocity is assumed to be $V_{hub} = 12$ m/s, which serves as input for estimating ten Kaimal PSDs calculated at equidistant points along the OWT, ranging from the Still Water Level (SWL) up to the top. A slight degree of randomness is introduced into the Kaimal PSD, adding stochasticity to the spectrum, as shown in Fig.10c. The JONSWAP PSD, displayed in Fig.10b, takes into account a wave height of $H_s = 6$ m and a wave period of $T_p = 10$ s in the fore-aft direction of the 5MW baseline OWT. The rotational sample of the moment spectrum of blade root bending, as seen in Fig.10a, assumes a rotor rotation frequency of 12.1 rpm. All these external vibration sources are stochastically simulated based on the theories described in Section 3. The excitation forces from these multiple hazards are combined, and the results are presented in Figs.10d,10d, 10d, and applied to the turbine to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed controls.

Figure 10: External force power spectrum density simulating the a) Blade rotation, b) JONSWAP wave sea surface elevation, c) Kaimal in different height levels along the turbine, d) Resultant PDS of combined spectra considering the Kaimal at the OWT tip, e) Resultant PDS considering the Kaimal along the turbine, and Resultant PDS considering the 'wind-random' Kaimal along the turbine (contaminated with 5% of white noise).

Figure 11 compare the tower's dynamic auto-spectral density (PSD) responses under unitary excitation, including wind, waves, and blade rotation. The transfer function used is the receptance FRF of the OWT, calculated for unitary excitation, where both mode shapes are well-defined. Under wave excitation, the OWT PSD response exhibits a

decrease in amplitude across the entire frequency range, with an additional peak at 0.14 Hz corresponding to the JONSWAP wave sea surface elevation. Wind excitation, on the other hand, amplifies the amplitude of the first mode while reducing that of the second mode due to the power density characteristic of the Kaimal spectrum. Blade rotation excitation amplifies the first resonant frequency and introduces significant resonance frequencies at 0.20 Hz, 0.4 Hz, and 0.6 Hz. When multiple hazard excitations, including rotation, waves, and wind, are combined, they impose higher amplitude amplification on the first mode and introduce resonant frequencies.

Figure 11: Comparison for the OWT top receptance response for unitary excitation (Transfer function - yellow line), PSD for wave excitation (blue line), PSD for wind excitation (orange line), PSD for wind excitation (orange line), PSD for blade rotation excitation (green line), PSD for the resultant combination of all excitation (purple line).

The external forces have a significant impact on the dynamic response of the OWT along its height. The receptance response is calculated along the OWT interface, encompassing points 0-10 as shown in Fig. 3a. Excitation sources are located at points 10 for blade rotation and unitary force, 4-10 for wind PSD, and 3 for wave excitation. Figure 12 displays the PSD response heatmap of the OWT without control over its interface. In this heatmap, the red marks indicate the highest amplitudes of each mode's resonance peak, while the bluish area represents anti-resonance and lower amplitudes. Figures 12a, 12b, and 12e show the PSD heatmaps of OWT height versus excitation frequency for unitary force, blade rotation excitation, and wave excitation, respectively. Figures 12c and 12d show the PSD heatmaps for Kaimal wind spectrum excitation, with and without a level of stochasticity. The combined PSD, encompassing all hazards, is presented in Fig 12f, representing the real application of offshore wind turbines. The first resonant frequency is the most affected by external forces, as evidenced by the height amplitude of displacement along the tower, indicated by the red frequency band ranging from 0 to 0.5 Hz and 2.4 Hz in Fig 12f. These frequencies correspond to the two resonant frequencies discussed in this paper.

Figure 12: Auto-spectrum PSD heatmaps of OWT's receptance response obtained along the turbine height versus excitation frequency for a) Unitary excitation, b) Blade rotation PSD excitation, c) Kaimal wind spectrum excitation, d) Kaimal with a small level of stochasticity spectrum excitation, e) JONSWAP wave excitation, f) Multiple hazard excitation.

Figure 13a displays the spectrogram of the auto-spectrum PSD of the wind turbine under multiple excitations across the entire frequency band. In Fig.13b, one can see the spectrogram zoomed around the first resonant frequency and in Fig.13c around the second resonant frequency. The spectrogram frequency was calculated using the spectrum-Matlab function, assuming a frequency resolution of $F_{res} = 40.0391$ mHz and a time resolution of $T_{res} = 59.9609$ s, and has as input the frequency and temporal acceleration response. The spectrogram illustrates how the frequency power content in the signal changes over time, where yellow presents the higher amplitudes and blue for the lower. The first resonant mode exhibits a higher amplitude in the analysed frequency band, which is enhanced by the force excitation. Therefore, the signal power is prominent in lower frequencies, and due to structural damping, it gradually decreases in amplitude over time.

Figure 13: Spectrogram of the wind turbine auto-spectrum under multiple excitations for a) whole frequency band (0 to 5Hz), b) zooming around the first resonant frequency, and c) zooming around the second resonant frequency. The frequency of the spectrogram calculated with the pspectrum Matlab function assumes $F_{res}=40.0391$ mHz, $T_{res} = 59.9609$ s.

The dynamic resonator is designed to operate at a specific frequency, and it is common for the target resonant frequency to split due to the dynamic coupling between resonators and the primary structure. This coupling introduces additional degrees of freedom around the target mode shape, resulting in other resonance frequencies emerging to the left and right of the operating frequency of the primary system controlled by the resonators. This passive vibration control system has a well-defined operational range. When it operates outside of this frequency range, it can lead to highly undesired behaviours, such as an increase in the amplitude of adjacent modes. The excitation forces from waves and blade rotation have resonant frequencies close to the first mode, which can pose challenges when implementing control in OWTs. We use the time signal's root mean square (RMS) value to quantify the vibration reduction achieved in each metamaterial OWT design. The RMS measures the amplitude of the wave time history signal and provides an amplitude value directly related to the energy content. This makes the RMS a suitable metric for quantifying the efficiency of vibration control. The percentage of vibration attenuation achieved by each control system is estimated using the response amplitude reduction (AMP_r), calculated by

$$AMP_r = 100 \left[\frac{RMS_{pc} - RMS_{mc}}{RMS_{pc}} \right] \quad (35)$$

where RMS_{pc} is the time signal RMS value for the uncontrolled turbine, and RMS_{mc} time signal RMS value for the metamaterial OWT. Figure 14 show the graphic of amplitude attenuation and amplification level achieved by the TMD and the metastructure turbine design to control the first, second, and first-second resonant frequencies. Control design varies in mass ratio from 5 to 30%, where below zero is considered reduction and above zero amplification on the RMS displacement amplitude level.

Figure 14: Amplitude level achieved by the TMD and the metastructures turbine design to control: a) the first resonant frequency, b) the second resonant frequency, c) first-second resonant frequencies. Control design varies in mass ratio from 5 to 30%.

The displacement amplitude calculations consider the entire temporal signal. Figure 14a presents the amplitude control data in table and bar graph formats for the TMD and the metamaterial turbine on top-, mid-, and along-configurations. The along-metamaterial configuration is the most effective configuration, which achieves a 30% reduction in OWT displacement under multiple hazard excitation. Figure 14b provides amplitude control data for the second mode only. Because the amplitude reduction calculations consider the entire temporal signal, the second frequency control using the RMS value intrinsic incorporates the first resonant frequency in the estimation, which has the highest amplitude and dominates the temporal response. In this case, the 'along' configuration exhibits the best amplitude control with a 5% mass ratio among the metamaterial configurations. Consequently, the amplitude reduction for the TMD installed at the middle length of the tower shows the best performance with a 10% mass ratio. Figure 14c displays the data and bar graph for the multiple control approach using only the metamaterial approach. The 'mid' and 'along' metastructure OWT configurations show the best performance with 19% and 25% attenuation for a 5% mass ratio. Beyond a 20% mass ratio, there is an increase in amplitude, indicated by negative values on the amplitude graphs. In all cases, a mass ratio lower than 20% has proven more efficient in reducing amplitude. This is because of the narrow frequency range between the first resonant peak and the excitation force frequency. A mass ratio exceeding 20% results in a significant shift and a wider frequency band in the controlled range. However, it aligns with the excitation frequency, amplifying displacement response rather than reducing it.

Figure 15: Auto-spectrum density and displacement of the OWT excited by multiple forces (wind, blade rotation, and waves) for the first resonant frequency control obtained at the tower tip controlled by a-b) TMD control installed on the top of WT, c-d) top-metastructure, e-f) mid-metastructure, and g-h) along-metastructure.

Figure 16: Spectrogram of the wind turbine auto-spectrum under multiple excitations controlling the first resonant frequency with a-d) TMD with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, e-h) top-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, i-l) mid-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, m-p) along-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%. The frequency of the spectrogram calculated with the pspectrum Matlab function assumes $F_{res}=40.0391$ mHz, $T_{res} = 59.960$ s.

Figure 15 presents the auto-spectrum density and displacement of the OWT for the first resonant frequency control in the frequency and time domains, respectively. Both responses are measured at the top of the tower and are excited by multiple forces, including wind, blade rotation, and waves. The control mass ratio is assumed to be 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, with a hysteretic damping factor of 0.03 applied uniformly across all design cases. The TMD's performance in both frequency and time domains is depicted in Figs.15a and 15b, showing a broad bandwidth related to the target frequency. However, the left peak of the split resonant mode experiences an increase in amplitude due to the excitation force. This amplification impacts the temporal response, where the displacement amplitudes exceed

those of the uncontrolled response.

OWT metastructure configurations for the top, middle, and along positions are shown in Figs.15c,15d,15e,15f,15g, and15h. The top configuration closely follows the TMD's behaviour, the mid configuration exhibits good attenuation up to a 10% mass ratio, and the along metamaterial configuration provides the best attenuation in the time domain for all tested mass ratios. Amplitude attenuation of the first resonant frequency by the controls aligns with the spectrograms shown in Fig.16, where spectrograms for controls designed with 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30% mass ratios are displayed in Figs.16a to 16d for the TMD, Figs.16e to 16h for the top metamaterial, Figs.16i to 16l for the mid metamaterial, and Figs.16m to 16p for the along metamaterial. The efficacy of the control is determined by the reduction of the yellow area on the spectrogram, indicating the decrease of overall power levels in the signal and, consequently, the vibration amplitude. In Fig.16, the yellow region indicates the power levels of the signal. The added control produces adjacent resonant peaks, with a strong component within the TMD control having a 30% mass ratio. The proposed metamaterials also exhibit consistent power levels in their maps despite having less intensity than in the TMD, validating the effectiveness of this approach in mitigating OWT vibration under multiple hazard excitations. Notably, the along metamaterial configuration attenuates the first resonant frequency best.

Frequency and temporal responses with resonators operating to control the second mode vibration are presented in Figs.17a and17b for the top configuration, Figs.17c and17d for the mid configuration, and Figs.17e and 17f for the along metamaterials. The resonators operate at a frequency of 2.39 Hz, where at this target frequency, the mid configuration demonstrates superior attenuation in the time domain response, especially for mass ratios up to 20%. Since the first mode exhibits higher amplitudes and consequently dominates the time response, the attenuation effect is less visible due to the different amplitudes between the modes. The shift in the target frequency caused by the control affects the first resonant mode and can increase displacement amplitude, as observed for mass ratios of 20% and 30% for both the top and mid metamaterials.

Spectrograms covering the second mode shapes with control applied only to the second mode for mass ratios of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30% are displayed in Figs. 18a to 18d for the top metamaterial, Figs. 18e to 18h for the mid metamaterial, and Figs. 18i to 18l for the along metamaterial. For better visualisation, a zoomed-in view around the second resonant frequency is applied to the figures. The resonators operate at 2.39 Hz, and with the bifurcation caused by the control, two additional resonant frequencies arise around 2.39 Hz (see Figure 15). Therefore, the right peak has a higher amplitude and dominates the power level. As we increase the control mass ratio, the larger the bandwidth imposed by the control; this phenomenon is seen in the spectrogram by the yellow area changing in frequency, also shown in Figure 15. The along- and mid-metamaterial configurations maintain response amplitudes, as evident in the temporal curves, while selectively attenuating the desired mode shape, as observed in the frequency domain.

Figure 17: Auto-spectrum density and displacement of the OWT excited by multiple forces (wind, blade rotation, and waves) for the second resonant frequency control obtained at the tower tip controlled by a-b) top-metastructure, c-d) mid-metastructure, and e-f) along-metastructure.

In the case of multiple-control metamaterials for OWTs, several resonances occur both before and after the bandgap, with some increasing amplitude and other minor mode shapes emerging around the gap of both target mode shapes. Despite the multiple-DOF metamaterials widening the attenuation bandwidth at the target frequency, localised vibration modes are observed within the local bandgap of the second mode for mass ratios exceeding 20%. These localised modes confine vibration energy to specific spatial regions along the OWT.

Metamaterial OWT configurations for the top, mid, and along positions in both frequency and time domains are presented in Figs.19a and 19b, Figs.19c and 19d, and Figs.19e and 19f, respectively. The 'top' configuration follows the TMD behaviour, the 'mid' configuration exhibits effective attenuation up to a 10% mass ratio, and the 'along' metamaterial configuration offers the best attenuation in the time domain across all tested mass ratios. Amplitude attenuation by the controls aligns with the spectrograms shown in Fig.20, where spectrograms for controls designed with mass ratios of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30% are displayed in Figs.20a to 20d for top metamaterial, Figs.20e to 20h

Figure 18: Spectrogram of the wind turbine auto-spectrum under multiple excitations controlling the second resonant frequency with a-d) top-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, e-h) mid-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, i-l) along-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%. The frequency of the spectrogram calculated with the pspectrum Matlab function assumes $F_{res}=40.0391$ mHz, $T_{res} = 59.960$ s.

for mid metamaterial, and Figs.20i to 20l for along metamaterial. Power levels remain consistent in the maps of the proposed metamaterials, confirming the efficiency of the proposed approach in controlling OWT vibration under multiple hazard excitations. The 'along' metamaterial configuration attenuates the first resonant frequency best and the second frequency well.

Figure 19: Auto-spectrum density and displacement of the OWT excited by multiple forces (wind, blade rotation, and waves) for the first and second resonant frequencies control obtained at the tower tip controlled by a-b) top-metastructure, c-d) mid-metastructure, and e-f) along-metastructure.

Figure 20: Spectrogram of the wind turbine auto-spectrum under multiple excitations controlling the first and second resonant frequencies with a-d) top-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, e-h) mid-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, i-l) along-metastructure with the mass ratio of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%. The frequency of the spectrogram calculated with the spectrum Matlab function assumes $F_{res}=40.0391$ mHz, $T_{res} = 59.960$ s.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated vibration mitigation in wind turbine design by incorporating metamaterials. Our approach involved modelling the dynamic behaviour of offshore wind turbines using the Spectral Element Method and considering multiple hazard excitation forces, including wave-wind-blade rotation, in accordance with international standards such as DNV-OS-J101, IEC, and JONSWAP. The results of our analysis demonstrate the effectiveness of implementing metamaterial concepts in OWT. We assessed the receptance responses of the turbine attached to a conventional TMD control system compared to our proposed wind turbine metastructure. We used dynamic response heatmaps and histogram graphics to demonstrate the advantages of using metamaterials over conventional passive devices. The metamaterial concept employed in this analysis is based on the theoretical foundation of infinite resonators. We established the formation of local bandgaps by analysing general linear attachments and utilising modal parameters of the basic structure, applying the root locus technique. Our study highlights the wind turbine metastructure as an efficient solution for vibration mitigation, even when subjected to multiple hazard excitation forces. A significant reduction in vibration amplitudes, achieving up to a 30% improvement when employing small-size resonators compared

to the conventional TMD, which reduces vibrations by only 7.8%. Furthermore, the importance of resonator design in the overall control strategy was emphasised, taking into account manufacturing and installation considerations. In contrast to conventional TMD controls, the wind turbine metastructure offers a unique combination of wide operational bandwidth and effective frequency attenuation. This achievement is made possible by employing smaller, less stiff mass control devices within the turbine structure.

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Appendix A. Analytical calculation of band gap edge frequencies

The analytical expression for the modal weightings $\bar{\eta}_n$ due to the coupling terms from the presence of the single degree of freedom vibration absorbers, with a closed-form expression [48]

$$\bar{\eta}_n = \frac{\bar{Q}_n}{\omega_n^2 - \Omega_n^2 \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon}{1 - \Omega_n^2}\right)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The roots of the denominator polynomial yield calculation of the new resonant frequencies for each mode, related to the two distinct resonances slit by the vibration absorber. The presence of an infinite number attached to the continuous structure will split the resonance of every mode shape. By considering a normalised excitation ($\Omega_n = \omega_n/\omega_r$) and the plain turbine natural ($\hat{\omega} = \omega/\omega_r$) frequencies by the resonator natural frequency (ω_r), two positive of the denominator is defined as

$$\omega^+ = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \epsilon + \Omega_n^2}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\Omega_n^2}{(1 + \epsilon + \Omega_n^2)^2}}\right)}, \quad \omega^- = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \epsilon + \Omega_n^2}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\Omega_n^2}{(1 + \epsilon + \Omega_n^2)^2}}\right)} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

the new resonances after the split of the target resonant frequency will be out of ranges $\omega_r < \omega < \omega_r\sqrt{1 + \epsilon}$. This frequency range defines the limits of the bandgap and provides an easy method for locating the bandgap at a target frequency. The bandwidth of the bandgap is determined by the mass ratio and attachment frequencies, given by $\Delta\omega = \omega_r(\sqrt{1 + \epsilon} - 1)$.

For multiple degrees of freedom, the analytical expression of the modal weightings is [62]

$$\bar{\eta}_n = \frac{\bar{Q}_n}{\omega_n^2 - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_1}{1 - \Omega^2} + \frac{\epsilon_2\beta^2}{\beta^2 - \Omega^2}\right)} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

In this case, one has a third-degree polynomial of the forms $\gamma^3 + d_1\gamma^2 + d_2\gamma + d_3 = 0$, where the three roots of the polynomial can be used to determine the three positive roots expressed as [62]

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_1 &= \left(\frac{1}{6}e_1^\dagger - 2\frac{e_2}{e_1^t} + e_3\right)^{0.5}, \quad \Omega_2 = \left(-\frac{1}{12}e_1^\dagger + \frac{e_2}{e_1^t} + e_3 + \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{2} \left(\frac{1}{6}e_1^\dagger + 2\frac{e_2}{e_1^t}\right)\right)^{0.5}, \\ \tilde{\Omega}_3 &= \left(-\frac{1}{12}e_1^\dagger + \frac{e_2}{e_1^t} + e_3 - \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{2} \left(\frac{1}{6}e_1^\dagger + 2\frac{e_2}{e_1^t}\right)\right)^{0.5} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where

$$e_1 = 36d_2d_1 - 108d_3 - 8d_1^3 + 12\sqrt{12d_3d_1^3 - 3d_2^2d_1^2 - 54d_2d_1d_3 + 12d_2^3 + 81d_3^2}, \quad e_2 = d_2 - \frac{1}{3}d_1^2, \quad e_3 = -\frac{1}{3}d_1$$

$$\gamma = \Omega^2, \quad d_1 = -(1 + \bar{\mu}_1 + \beta^2(1 + \bar{\mu}_2) + \Omega_k^2), \quad d_2 = \beta^2(1 + \bar{\mu}_1 + \bar{\mu}_2) + (1 + \beta^2)\Omega_k^2, \quad d_3 = -\beta^2\Omega_k^2$$

On a limiting analysis of the variable ω_n from 0 to ∞ for the three roots, one has

$$\lim_{\omega_n \rightarrow 0} \Omega_1 = \beta^+, \quad \lim_{\omega_n \rightarrow \infty} \Omega_1 = \infty, \quad \lim_{\omega_n \rightarrow 0} \Omega_2 = 0, \quad \lim_{\omega_n \rightarrow \infty} \Omega_2 = 1, \quad \lim_{\omega_n \rightarrow 0} \Omega_3 = \beta^-, \quad \lim_{\omega_n \rightarrow \infty} \Omega_3 = \beta^+ \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where β^+ and β^- are defined as

$$\beta^- = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \epsilon_1 + \beta^2(1 + \epsilon_2)}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\beta^2(1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)}{(1 + \epsilon_1 + \beta^2(1 + \epsilon_2))^2}} \right)},$$

$$\beta^+ = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \epsilon_1 + \beta^2(1 + \epsilon_2)}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\beta^2(1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)}{(1 + \epsilon_1 + \beta^2(1 + \epsilon_2))^2}} \right)}$$

By normalising the third-degree polynomial and multiplying the derived band gap edge frequencies by the first target resonator frequency ω_{r1} , it predicted the new resonant frequencies appearing in two ranges, which are defined by

$$\omega_{r1} < \hat{\Omega} < \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\omega}_{r1}^2(1 + \epsilon_1) + \hat{\omega}_{r2}^2(1 + \epsilon_2)}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\beta^2(1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)}{(1 + \epsilon_1 + \beta^2(1 + \epsilon_2))^2}} \right)}$$

$$\omega_{r2} < \hat{\Omega} < \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\omega}_{r1}^2(1 + \epsilon_1) + \hat{\omega}_{r2}^2(1 + \epsilon_2)}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\beta^2(1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)}{(1 + \epsilon_1 + \beta^2(1 + \epsilon_2))^2}} \right)} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Appendix B. OWT finite element modelling

In open FAST code[59, 67], NREL's primary physics-based engineering program for simulating the coupled dynamic response of wind turbines, the NREL 5 MW monopile is modelled using the finite element method. The tower is represented with a 3D-element Timoshenko beam, employing two nodes and six degrees of freedom (DOF) per node, which include three translational displacements u , v , w , and three rotational degrees of freedom θ_u , θ_v , θ_w , with respect to the x-, y-, and z-axes, respectively. The nodal displacement of the element is defined as follows

$$\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, v_1, w_1, \theta_{u1}, \theta_{v1}, \theta_{w1}, u_2, v_2, w_2, \theta_{u2}, \theta_{v2}, \theta_{w2}\}^T \quad (\text{B.1})$$

for subscripts 1 and 2 denoting the element node-one and -two, respectively. The lumped mass representing the Nacelle-rotor is defined by the matrix \mathbf{m}_{lu} , mass and stiffness matrices for the three-dimensional finite Timoshenko beam element are defined as [67]

$$\mathbf{M}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11}^e & \mathbf{M}_{12}^e \\ \mathbf{M}_{21}^e & \mathbf{M}_{22}^e \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{11}^e & \mathbf{K}_{12}^e \\ \mathbf{K}_{21}^e & \mathbf{K}_{22}^e \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{m}_{lu} = \text{diag}[m_{rna}, m_{rna}, m_{rna}, J_{nac}, J_{hub}, 0] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where m_{rna} is the RNA mass, J_{hub} the hub inertia, and J_{nac} is the nacelle inertia about the yaw axis. The matrices components $(\cdot)_{11}^e$ and $(\cdot)_{22}^e$ describe the interdependency of the DOFs of the first and second node, respectively, $(\cdot)_{12}^e$

and $(\cdot)_{21}^e$ is the interconnection between both diagonal variables. M_{22}^e and K_{22}^e are similar to M_{11}^e and K_{11}^e respectively, except for the sign of the off-diagonal entries, the mass element matrix is given

$$\mathbf{M}_{11}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{13}{35} + \frac{6I_z}{5Ale^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{11le}{210} + \frac{I_z}{10Ale} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{13}{35} + \frac{6I_y}{5Ale^2} & 0 & -\frac{11le}{210} + \frac{I_y}{10Ale} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{I_p}{3A} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{11le}{210} + \frac{I_y}{10Ale} & 0 & \frac{le^2}{105} + \frac{2I_y}{15A} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{11le}{210} + \frac{I_z}{10Ale} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{le^2}{105} + \frac{2I_z}{15A} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{21}^e = \mathbf{M}_{21}^{eT} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{6} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{9}{70} - \frac{6I_z}{5Ale^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{13le}{420} + \frac{I_y}{10Ale} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{9}{70} - \frac{6I_y}{5Ale^2} & 0 & -\frac{13le}{410} + \frac{I_y}{10Ale} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{I_p}{6A} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{13le}{420} - \frac{I_y}{10Ale} & 0 & -\frac{le^2}{140} - \frac{2I_y}{30A} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{13le}{420} + \frac{I_z}{10Ale} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{le^2}{140} - \frac{2I_z}{30A} \end{bmatrix}$$

and the stiffness components by

$$\mathbf{K}_{11}^e = \frac{1}{le^3} \begin{bmatrix} Ale^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{12EI_z}{1+P_y} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{6EI_zle}{1+P_y} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{12EI_y}{1+P_z} & 0 & -\frac{6EI_yle}{1+P_z} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & GI_tle^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{6EI_yle}{1+P_z} & 0 & -\frac{EI_yle^2(4+P_z)}{1+P_z} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{6EI_zle}{1+P_y} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{EI_zle^2(4+P_z)}{1+P_y} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{21}^e = \mathbf{K}_{21}^{eT} = \begin{bmatrix} -EAle^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{12EI_z}{1+P_y} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{6EI_zle}{1+P_y} \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{12EI_y}{1+P_z} & 0 & \frac{6EI_yle}{1+P_z} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -GI_tle^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{6EI_yle}{1+P_z} & 0 & \frac{EI_yle^2(2-P_z)}{1+P_z} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{6EI_zle}{1+P_y} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{EI_zle^2(2+P_y)}{1+P_y} \end{bmatrix}$$

where le is the beam element le , thickness t , cross-section A , D_t denotes the tubular cross-section outer diameter, and inner diameter is given by $Di = (D_t - 2t)$. Assuming an isotropic, linear elastic material with density ρ , Young's modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν , the shear modulus can be expressed as $G = \frac{E}{2(\nu+1)}$. The second moment of area is denoted as I_y and I_z , while the polar moment of inertia is I_p , and the constant I_t represents the element's torsion. In the 5MW OWT modelled with FEM, 30 elements were assumed in the mesh, and similar geometrical and material properties and unitary excitation are described in section 2. The WT is excited by a unitary force, and the flexural and rotational responses were estimated at the top of the tower. The validation of the OWT SEM with FEM was performed using the receptance response.

Figure B.21: Flexural (LHS) and rotational (RHS) receptance FRF modelled by FEM and SEM obtained on the WT top.

Figure B.22: Flexural receptance FRF modelled by FEM and SEM obtained on the along metamaterial turbine with controlled actuating at first (LHS) and second (RHS) resonant frequencies.

In Figure B.21, the flexural and rotational receptance FRFs of the OWT are compared, which are modelled with both SEM and FEM. The receptance FRFs are obtained at the zx -plane of the WT, as shown in figure 1. The responses of the WT estimated with SEM are analogous to the receptance response obtained from FEM. Furthermore, Figure B.22 compares the along metamaterial turbine modelled with both methods. The control operates with 5% of mass ratio and actuates at first and second resonant frequencies. Throughout these analyses, both the turbine and along metamaterial turbine modelled with SEM accurately capture the dynamic behaviour of the turbines modelled with the FEM formulation given in FAST. It is worth mentioning that these results validate the proposed spectral approach and the mechanical metamaterial design incorporated in the wind turbine.

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